

Coral Community Characterization of Turneffe Atoll Marine Reserve, 2025

Turneffe Atoll Sustainability Association:

Virginia Burns-Perez, Kevin Novelo

University of Belize Environmental Research Institute:

Jessica C. Boles, Anthony Lizama, Jake L. Snaddon

University of Belize Environmental Research Institute & Boston University:

Ninon Martinez

April 25, 2025

1. Background

The Turneffe Atoll Marine Reserve (TAMR), co-managed by the Turneffe Atoll Sustainability Association (TASA), is the largest marine protected area in Belize. Spanning approximately 360,000 acres, TAMR encompasses diverse and ecologically significant habitats, including expansive coral reef systems, over 27,000 acres of mangroves, and vast seagrass beds. These ecosystems play a critical role in supporting biodiversity and providing essential ecosystem services to stakeholders in Belize City, Caye Caulker, San Pedro, and the northern communities of Copper Bank, Chunox, and Sarteneja.

On November 2, 2022, Hurricane Lisa, a Category 1 storm, passed directly over TAMR, causing damage to marine and coastal ecosystems, as well as significant destruction in Belize City. In response to this event, the Mesoamerican Reef Insurance Program for Belize was activated, leading to the first payout for immediate recovery and restoration efforts within the Turneffe Atoll reef system. This parametric insurance policy was financed by the Mesoamerican Reef Fund (MAR Fund) and WTW's Climate and Resilience Hub, with co-funding from the InsuResilience Solutions Fund. Unlike traditional insurance models, parametric insurance provides rapid financial support

based on predefined environmental triggers, ensuring timely resources for post-disaster recovery and resilience-building initiatives.

To maximize the effectiveness of these recovery efforts, TASA and MAR Fund formalized a Grant Agreement (No. RRI-029-2022), later revised through a Grant Agreement Modification Letter in September 2023. These modifications, finalized on May 13, 2024, realigned initial recovery activities with the evolving needs of TAMR, focusing on enhancing resilience, operational capacity, and long-term sustainability. This includes strategic investments in equipment procurement, infrastructure improvements, staff training, and emergency preparedness.

One critical component of TAMR's recovery strategy was assessing the health and resilience of its coral reef ecosystems, particularly considering ongoing stressors such as Stony Coral Tissue Loss Disease (SCTLD) and coral bleaching. This technical report documents the most extensive Comprehensive Coral Reef Assessment for TAMR to date, conducted using the Atlantic & Gulf Rapid Reef Assessment (AGRRA) Coral Reef Monitoring Methodology. The primary objective of this assessment was to evaluate coral condition post-Hurricane Lisa and determine the prevalence of bleaching, SCTLD, and other diseases. By systematically monitoring reef conditions, this study aims to inform adaptive management strategies, enhance conservation planning, and directly guide restoration interventions at Turneffe Atoll Marine Reserve.

2. Methods

To complete the coral reef assessment, the Atlantic and Gulf Rapid Reef Assessment (AGRRA) Coral Protocol was used (Lang et al., 2015). Theory and practical training in AGRRA Coral Protocol Revision: 2023-04-14 ©Ocean Research & Education methods (AGRRA, 2023) were validated before field surveys to ensure consistency and accuracy among surveyors. These surveys were all conducted on SCUBA between June and October 2024.

Figure 1. Map of sampled localities

2.1 Site/Field Site Validation Methods

2.1.1 Site Selection

Forty localities were selected across TAMR (Figure 1). Nine of the 40 localities were long-term reef monitoring sites in Turneffe with existing GPS points and/or marker buoys (see Table 1). The remaining 31 localities were selected along a linear tract around TAMR where there was evidence of reef structure (based on satellite imagery) with a minimum distance of 1.4 kilometers between localities. Within a 500-meter radius of each locality, 2 fore-reef sites were selected to represent a shallow (5-10 meter depth) and deep (10-15 meter depth) reef of that locality.

2.1.2 Habitat Validation

The sites at each locality were validated visually as being representative of reef structure. Gorgonian plains and sand flats were not considered reef in this survey. Sites that did not meet the criteria were not surveyed.

2.1.3 Sampling Area

Two to three 10 x 1 meter belt transects were used to survey each site. Following the coral AGRRA protocol, transects were laid haphazardly across representative reef structure, avoiding large areas of sand and rubble. Surveyors worked within a 1000 m² (~30 x 30 meter) area, keeping each transect a minimum of 5 meters apart from each other.

2.2 Coral Sampling Methods

2.2.1 Individual Identification

Within the 10 x 1 meter belt transects, all stony coral colonies (Appendix Table 1) with a maximum diameter of at least 4 cm were identified, measured, and assessed for signs of mortality, bleaching, and diseases/syndromes.

2.2.2 Coral Measurements

Corals were evaluated based on their orientation of growth. The length (L, cm) of the colony was measured as the maximum diameter parallel to the substrate on which it was growing. The width (W, cm) of the colony was measured as the maximum length perpendicular to the colony length. The height (H, cm) was measured as the maximum height perpendicular to the substrate on which the coral was growing.

2.2.3 Coral Mortality

Coral mortality was estimated as a percent of the colony without living tissue. They were classified as recent mortality (RM), transitional mortality (TM), or old mortality (OM) based on exposure of coral skeleton. Recent mortality was quantified as percent of the colony with exposed skeleton only with no skeletal degradation. Transitional mortality

was quantified as percent of the colony with visible skeleton with other organisms growing over the skeleton with minimal skeletal degradation. Old mortality was classified as percent of the colony with no visible skeleton beneath organisms overgrowing it with skeletal degradation.

2.2.4 Signs of Disease

Signs of disease were confirmed by the presence of coral tissue necrosis or lesions. Descriptive signs like color and shapes of lesions (blotches, bands) were also identified.

2.2.5 Signs of Bleaching

Signs of bleaching were considered signs of coloration on the colony inconsistent with the surveyor's previous experience of what the coral's typical color would be. Corals were classified as pale (PA) appearing a color lighter than typical or bleached (BL) appearing with blotches of white or wholly appearing white, the color of the coral skeleton.

2.2.6 Classification of Coral Functional Groups

Corals were assessed and characterized by functional groups, morphological groups, and vulnerability to SCTLTD to determine each group's relative abundance across the atoll. Functional groups were classified as competitive, weedy, generalist, or stress-tolerant (Darling et al., 2012). Shape groups were classified as platy-foliaceous-encrusting, massive-nodular, or branching-ramose-phaceloid (Alvarez-Filip et al., 2011). Vulnerability to SCTLTD was classified as low, moderate, or high (Lee Hing et al., 2022; Papke et al., 2024) (Appendix Table 1).

2.3 Data Processing

After data collection, the datasheets were digitized and manually cleaned by the data collectors. They were then processed using a revised version of the coral community characterization validation script in `Validation.Rmd` from Boles et al. (2024). The script was updated to accommodate slight methodological changes in this year's survey compared to previous ones.

R Statistical Software (R Core Team 2023) was also used to create the figures and tables in this report, with the exception of Figure 1, which was made using ArcGIS. The primary R packages used were `tidyverse`, `readxl`, `ggpubr`, `vegan`, and `ggrepel`. The R packages `sf`, `ggspatial`, and `ggnewscale` were used to make the maps.

3. Results

In total, 38 localities were surveyed, as two localities did not meet the criteria for inclusion, resulting in 153 transects, 6,992 corals, 39 unique species, 210 instances of stony coral tissue loss disease (SCTLD), and 1,688 instances of bleaching. The highest number of unique species (22) was recorded at locality NW04.C. The most SCTLD instances (23) were found at NW06.C, while the lowest (0) occurred at 14 localities. The highest number of bleaching instances (105, including both pale and fully bleached corals) was recorded at CW01.C, whereas the lowest (15) was observed at CE01.C (Table 1).

Across localities, the relative abundance of different coral shapes was relatively consistent, with 84% Massive-Nodular corals, 12% Platy-Foliaceous-Encrusting corals, and 4% Branching-Ramose-Phaceloid corals. Locality CW04.C had a distinctly higher proportion (32%) of Platy-Foliaceous-Encrusting compared to other localities (Figure 2A; Table 2).

Coral trait composition varied across localities, with weedy corals composing 41-78%, stress-tolerant corals composing 12-53%, generalist corals composing 0-19%, and competitive corals composing 0-1.5%. The standard deviation between localities was highest for stress-tolerant corals, with 10.2, with Locality SE02.C having only 12% stress-tolerant corals, and Locality SE04.C having 53% stress-tolerant corals (Figure 2B; Table 2).

While corals with high susceptibility to SCTLD were relatively uncommon across TAMR (2.1%), the proportion of corals with low versus moderate susceptibility varied by locality. Corals with moderate susceptibility ranged from 20% at Locality NE04.C to 62% at Locality SE04.C, with a standard deviation of 11.2. Corals with low susceptibility ranged from 35% at Locality SE04.C to 77% at Locality NE04.C, with a standard deviation of 11.3 (Figure 2C; Table 2).

Table 1. Sampling effort for 2025 coral community characterization by locality, exposure type, sampled transects, sampled coral, unique species sampled, instances of SCTL D, and instances of bleaching. Both locality code and label are provided. Data from TAMR.

Locality Code	Locality Label	Exposure	Transects	Sampled Corals	Unique Species	SCTL D #	Bleach #
*1062	SW01.C	Leeward	4	117	16	18	38
*1071	NE08.C	Windward	4	152	12	0	21
*1206	SE02.C	Windward	4	191	18	0	28
*CB	SE08.C	Windward	4	95	14	6	52
CM01	NE01.C	Windward	4	158	11	1	20
CM02	NE02.C	Windward	4	103	12	2	28
CM03	NE03.C	Windward	4	139	13	1	18
CM04	NE04.C	Windward	4	131	10	2	17
CM05	NE05.C	Windward	4	121	14	0	23
CM06	NE07.C	Windward	4	177	14	15	85
CM07	CE01.C	Windward	4	147	12	0	15
CM08	CE02.C	Windward	4	188	15	0	19
CM09	CE03.C	Windward	4	150	17	0	26
CM10	CE04.C	Windward	4	235	16	0	43
CM11	CE06.C	Windward	4	183	21	3	24
CM12	CE07.C	Windward	6	205	18	0	34
CM13	SE01.C	Windward	4	182	13	0	39
CM14	SE03.C	Windward	4	239	13	10	56
CM15	SE04.C	Windward	4	207	14	4	82
CM16	SE05.C	Windward	4	173	17	0	24
CM17	SE06.C	Windward	4	160	15	16	62
CM18	SE07.C	Windward	4	166	14	9	85
CM20	SW03.C	Leeward	4	202	14	3	76
CM21	SW02.C	Leeward	2	44	8	0	16
CM22	CW06.C	Leeward	4	136	18	15	70
CM23	CW05.C	Leeward	4	163	15	7	69
CM24	CW04.C	Leeward	4	319	19	1	21
CM25	CW02.C	Leeward	4	182	14	12	84
CM26	CW01.C	Leeward	4	252	14	20	105
CM27	NW06.C	Leeward	4	299	14	23	101
CM28	NW05.C	Leeward	4	150	15	3	39
CM29	NW04.C	Leeward	4	263	22	1	20
CM31	NW02.C	Leeward	4	173	13	0	25
*CZ2	NE06.C	Windward	4	186	12	0	63
*MP	NW01.C	Leeward	4	184	15	10	40
*SP	CE05.C	Windward	5	328	16	6	42
*WP4	CW03.C	Leeward	4	310	16	0	36
*WP5	NW03.C	Leeward	4	182	14	22	42
38 localities		2 exposures	153 transects	6992 coral	39 species	210 SCTL D	1688 bleached

*the long-term reef monitoring sites

Figure 2. Column plot of coral shape (A), coral traits (B), and susceptibility to SCTL D (C) at TAMR localities, presented as relative abundance of total sampled coral.

Table 2. Table of coral attribute values for 2025 coral community characterization by attribute type, including overall percent of sampled coral, and the minimum, mean, median, maximum, and standard deviation of percent by locality. Data from TAMR.

Attribute	Value	Overall	By Locality				
		Percentage	Min	Mean	Median	Max	SD
Coral Shape	Branching-Ramose-Phaceloid	3.8	0	3.7	3.3	10.5	2.2
	Massive-Nodular	84.4	63.3	85.6	87	97.7	7.4
	Platy-Foliaceous-Encrusting	11.8	0.8	10.8	8.4	32	6.7
Coral Traits	Competitive	0.1	0	0.1	0	1.5	0.3
	Generalist	7.7	0	7.3	6.7	19	5.3
	Stress-tolerant	29.8	12	31	31.7	53.1	10.2
	Weedy	62.4	41	61.6	61	77.7	9.6
SCTLD Susceptibility	High	2.1	0	2.2	1.9	7.4	1.7
	Low	60.1	35.3	59.3	59.6	77.1	11.3
	Moderate	37.7	19.8	38.4	37	62.3	11.2

Coral shape is relatively consistent between the two sampled reef zones of deep fore reef and shallow fore reef (Figure 3; Figure 6A). For coral traits, weedy corals are slightly more common (Table 2; Figure 4; Figure 6B), as well as corals with low susceptibility to SCTLD (Table 2; Figure 5; Figure 6C). Sites with a leeward exposure in comparison to a windward exposure were found to have a greater proportion of Platy-Foliaceous-Encrusting corals, generalist and stress-tolerant corals, and corals with moderate susceptibility to SCTLD (Figure 7).

Figure 3. Map of coral shape proportions at sampled shallow fore reef (A) and deep fore reef (B) sites across TAMR.

Figure 4. Map of coral trait proportions at sampled shallow fore reef (A) and deep fore reef (B) sites across TAMR.

Figure 5. Map of stony coral tissue loss disease susceptibility proportions at sampled shallow fore reef (A) and deep fore reef (B) sites across TAMR

Figure 6. Column plot of coral shape (A), coral traits (B), and susceptibility to SCTL D (C) at TAMR reef zones (either deep fore reef or shallow fore reef), presented as relative abundance of total sampled coral.

Figure 7. Column plot of coral shape (A), coral traits (B), and susceptibility to SCTL D (C) at TAMR reef exposure types (either leeward or windward), presented as relative abundance of total sampled coral.

Coral community diversity varied across localities with a relatively normal distribution. Species richness (standardized to a minimum sample size of 44 individual coral), ranged from 7 to 12, with a mean of 9 and standard deviation of 1.3. Shannon Diversity Index values ranged from 1 to 2, with a mean of 1.8 and standard deviation of 0.2. Coral abundance per transect varied widely, from 22 to 80, with a mean of 45 and standard deviation of 14. These findings highlight differences in coral diversity and abundance across TAMR localities (Figure 8; Table 3). When looking at site-level diversity (standardized to a minimum sample size of 9 coral), several sites had outlier diversity metrics, however none that ranged far outside the minima or maxima (Figure 9; Figure 10). Diversity metrics did not vary greatly by exposure type or reef zone (Figure 11).

Table 3. Table of summary statistics metrics for 2025 coral community characterization diversity metrics, including minimum, mean, median, and maximum values for localities, as well as the standard deviation. Diversity metrics include species richness standardized to minimal sample of n = 44, Shannon Diversity Index, and average abundance per transect. Data from TAMR.

Diversity Metric for Localities	Min	Mean	Median	Max	SD
Richness	6.84	9.37	9.17	12.48	1.34
Shannon	1.05	1.79	1.77	2.31	0.24
Transect Abundance	22	45.41	43.75	79.75	14.19

Figure 8. Column plot of species richness standardized to minimal sample of $n = 44$ (A), Shannon Diversity Index (B), and average abundance per transect (C) at TAMR sampled localities for corals.

Figure 9. Map of species richness at sampled shallow fore reef (A) and deep fore reef (B) sites across TAMR

Figure 10. Boxplot of species richness standardized to minimal sample of $n = 9$ (A), Shannon Diversity Index (B), and average abundance per transect (C), for sites at TAMR for corals, presented as a boxplot of values separated by reef zone (either deep fore reef or shallow fore reef).

Figure 11. Boxplot of species richness standardized to minimal sample of $n = 26$ (A), Shannon Diversity Index (B), and abundance per transect (C), for sites at TAMR, presented as a boxplot of values separated by reef zone (either deep fore reef or shallow fore reef).

Distribution of key taxa varied across the atoll (Figure 12). Dominant coral taxa *Agaricia*, *Porites astreoides*, and *Porites porites* were found across all localities, with the exception of *Porites porites* being absent from CE01.C and SW02.C (Figure 13A). The reef-building genus *Orbicella* was present at most localities, apart from NE01.C. However, the other main reef-builder coral genus *Acropora* was notably absent from most localities, being found only at CE03.C and CE05.C (Figure 13A). Stress-tolerant coral taxa *Colpophyllia*, *Diploria*, and *Pseudodiploria* were each present and absent at a variety of localities. Localities SW01.C, CE02.C, CE03.C, and NW04.C notably contained all three taxa, and localities NE08.C, SE02.C, CE01.C, SW02.C, CW01.C, NW02.C, and CW03.C contained none of the three (Figure 13C).

Average stony coral tissue loss disease (SCTLD) instances per site varied by locality, though were less frequent than bleaching instances, which were found upwards of 45 times per site in localities such as CM25, CW01.C, and NW06.C (Figure 14; Figure 15; Figure 16). Sparse cases of other diseases, including black band disease, ciliates, dark spots disease, and yellow band disease were observed (Figure 17). While most corals across the atoll had less than $\frac{1}{3}$ dead tissues, some sites, such as CW04.C, had a high proportion of corals with more than $\frac{2}{3}$ dead tissues (Figure 18).

Ecological volume of *Orbicella* coral individuals (cm^3) varied by Locality by order of magnitude, with NE06.C having a very low narrow distribution with individuals less than 100cm^3 in size, and NE03.C having a median ecological volume over $100,000\text{cm}^3$ in size (Figure 20).

Figure 12. Map of presence/absence of taxa of interest at Turneffe Atoll, including dominant taxa *Agaricia*, *Porites astreoides*, and *Porites porites*, key reef-builders *Acropora* and *Orbicella*, and stress-tolerant taxa *Colpophyllia*, *Diploria*, and *Pseudodiploria*. Grey slices on the pie graphs indicate an absence of a taxa, whereas colored slices indicate presence of the taxa of the corresponding color.

Figure 13. Tile plot of presence/absence of taxa of interest at Turneffe Atoll including dominant taxa *Agaricia*, *Porites astreoides*, and *Porites porites* (A), key reef-builders

Acropora and *Orbicella* (B), and stress-tolerant taxa *Colpophyllia*, *Diploria*, and *Pseudodiploria* (C). Red cells indicate an absence, and green cells indicate a presence.

Figure 14. Tile plot of average count of instances of health concerns (stony coral tissue loss disease and coral bleaching) for each locality at Turneffe Atoll.

Figure 15. Map of stony coral tissue loss disease instances at sampled shallow fore reef (A) and deep fore reef (B) sites across Turneffe Atoll.

Figure 16. Map of bleaching instances at sampled shallow fore reef (A) and deep fore reef (B) sites across Turneffe Atoll.

Figure 17. Map of disease prevalence (excluding stony coral tissue loss disease) across Turneffe Atoll shallow fore reef (A) and deep fore reef (B) sites.

Figure 18. Map of percent of dead tissue on living corals across Turneffe Atoll shallow fore reef (A) and deep fore reef (B) site.

Figure 19. Map of recruits instances at sampled shallow fore reef (A) and deep fore reef (B) sites across TAMR.

Table 4. Table of overall coral recruit counts by taxa and overall at TAMR.

Organism	Recruits
<i>Porites astreoides</i>	661
<i>Siderstrea siderea</i>	363
<i>Siderastrea radians</i>	130
<i>Stephanocoenia intersepta</i>	91
<i>Agaricia spp.</i>	82
<i>Montastrea cavernosa</i>	39
<i>Porites spp.</i>	21
Other	84
22 taxa	1471 recruits

Figure 20. Boxplot of ecological volume of *Orbicella* coral (cm^3) by Locality at Turneffe Atoll, presented as a boxplot of values with a log y-axis separated by reef exposure (either leeward or windward). Ecological volume is calculated as πHr^2 for each coral, where H is maximum height, and r is equal to $(\text{maximum width} + \text{maximum length})/4$ (Shaish et al., 2006).

4. Discussion

The stony (Scleractinian) coral community of Turneffe Atoll across 40 windward fore-reef and leeward reef slope locations had similar coral community compositions (Table 1; Figure 2; Figure 6; Figure 7). Relative abundance of massive-nodular corals, those that create mounding and generally spherical structures (Alvarez-Filip et al., 2011) dominated across all sites (Figure 2A; Table 2; Figure 3), however, these were comprised of mainly “weedy” (Darling et al., 2012) species that don’t provide a significant structural framework to the reef (Guendulain-García et al., 2023) (Figure 2B; Table 2; Figure 4). This is aligned with the evidenced regional trends of reef shifts to “flattened” structure (Alvarez-Filip et al., 2009). The implications of this are that the coral are not serving their expected complex structural function (Alvarez-Filip et al., 2013).

One of the primary “reef-building” genera, *Orbicella*, occurred across all but one locality, though mostly present on shallow fore reef sites (Figure 12; Figure 13). Though not dominant, *Orbicella* is still persistent on the reef. *Orbicella* provides major reef structure and framework, so not only presence, but the ecological volume of the individuals matter to infer functional reef space (Williams et al., 2015). The *Orbicella* of Turneffe all have large ecological volumes, suggesting their presence serves ecological function (Figure 20). Dead or alive, *Orbicella* provides a solid structural base to overall reef architecture, and has a morphology with a low surface area to volume ratios, allowing for slower bio-erosion (Medellín-Maldonado et al., 2023). Branching corals in the genus *Acropora* were encountered only at two sites (CE03.C, CE05.5). They are primary reef-builders providing major structure to reefs, but not persistent across Turneffe. Considerations for successful coral restoration are 1.) natural conditions that allow for persistence and 2.) available native species.

The overall diversity of species across sites varies minimally across the atoll (Table 3; Figure 8, Figure 9, Figure 10, Figure 11), with no sites having all key taxa (dominant taxa *Agaricia*, *Porites astreoides*, and *Porites porites*; key reef-builders *Acropora* and *Orbicella*, and; stress-tolerant taxa *Colpophyllia*, *Diploria*, and *Pseudodiploria*) represented (Figure 12; Figure 13). The reefs, once considered highly diverse, are no longer representative of a diverse marine environment. We are not seeing functional diversity nor functional redundancy of corals among reef corals as space-fillers and reef builders (Alvarez-Filip et al., 2011). While coral recruits are prevalent across all TAMR sites, indicating reproduction, a fundamental ecological process, the taxonomic composition of the species that are successfully reproducing are dominantly those of non-reef-building species of the primarily “weedy” guild (Edmunds, 2023) (Table 4; Figure 19).

Recent threats to reef corals have been bleaching from heat stress (Helgoe et al., 2024) and Stony Coral Tissue Loss Disease (SCTLD) related death (Papke et al., 2024). Signs of coral bleaching were present at all sites (Figure 16), which may adversely affect future reproductive success (Johnston et al., 2020), increase their vulnerability to disease-related death (Brodnicke et al., 2019), and affect their overall survivorship. However, repeated bleaching on an individual does not have a significant effect on growth. Survivorship is a more consistent predictor of future coral growth than whether or not corals are bleached, making it a more reliable indicator to consider for restoration intervention (McCarthy et al., 2024).

SCTLD was the region's greatest threat to coral survivorship (Alvarez-Filip et al., 2022) in recent years. Though we encountered a moderate amount of SCTLD across TAMR sites (Figure 15), we had limited encounters of meandroid corals, those most vulnerable to SCTLD, across all sites (Figure 5). Only 4 localities (CE02, CE03, NW04, SW01) had occurrences of all 3 main meandroid genera, *Colpophyllia*, *Diploria*, and *Pseudodiploria*: this low occurrence rate may be linked to the 2021 SCTLD outbreak in the atoll. Notably, there were no encounters of *Dendrogyra cylindrus*, indicating a possible local extinction.

Across Turneffe, other coral diseases have minimal prevalence, with most sites not having any signs of other diseases at all (Figure 17). Patterns of bleaching and disease prevalence are not evident from this atoll-wide assessment, but what is evident is that SCTLD has greater prevalence on the leeward side of the atoll (Figure 15).

Across the atoll, many coral colonies experienced partial colony mortality, with a little more than half being fully alive. At most sites, there are colonies with different degrees of mortality high (>2/3 dead), moderate (1/3 – 2/3 dead), low (<1/3 dead), and none, which may suggest different degrees of vulnerability to causes of mortality (Figure 18). The causes of these corals' individual mortality cannot be linked to a particular event or stressor, but there are no signs of refugia from coral mortality among these sites. Possible causes of coral mortality are thermal stress and disease (Brown et al., 2023; Spadafore et al., 2021). Tracking survival and associated environmental conditions can correlate possible bleaching or disease related mortality. Physical or biogeochemical environmental conditions influence bleaching, so further investigation into these conditions across the atoll would be needed (Helgoe et al., 2024).

This assessment of coral species across Turneffe Atoll was intended to inform adaptive management. Generally, restoration and protection are adaptive actions for marine ecosystems; protection is considered a passive intervention, where implementation typically takes longer than restoration because it requires legislative support

(Boström-Einarsson et al., 2020; Hughes et al., 2010). Restoration, an active intervention, can be implemented along a shorter timeline. Restoration considerations include 1.) candidate species for restoration 2.) sites for source material, and 3.) sites for restoration (Baums, 2019). Metrics for successful ecological restoration are not standardized, and short timelines for projects do not ensure achievement of objectives (Boström-Einarsson et al., 2020; Mulà et al., 2025). The practicality of implementation is one of the greatest considerations for restoration projects; if selected sites are not accessible for field teams, restoration efforts may not be realistically feasible, which can undermine the consistency and robustness of long-term monitoring programs (Mulà et al., 2025).

5. Recommendations

Potential areas for source material could be Atoll-wide. However, areas for restoration would ideally be where the coral population could naturally, successfully propagate. They should ideally have high coral abundance and species richness, presence of key taxa, low bleaching levels, and low SCTL and disease levels. In addition, potential areas for restoration must be practically accessible for field teams. This leads Central-East Turneffe to be the most promising area at TAMR (Table 5).

From this assessment, we can identify candidate species as those with ecological importance and sufficient population numbers: *Orbicella* spp., *Acropora* spp., and *Agaricia* spp (Table 6).

Other considerations:

1. Longitudinal tracking of survival, bleaching, and disease of coral colonies to infer possible causes of mortality and coral populations resistant to stressors.
2. Assessment of where species broadcast spawn would naturally distribute.
3. Assessment of coral holobiont to assess genetic and microbial communities that may contribute to species resistance and resilience.
4. Incorporating natural ecological processes into restoration (Ladd et al., 2018)

Table 5. Demonstration of pros/cons for the recommendation of Central-East Turneffe as an area of recommendation. Pros/cons are written relative to other surveyed areas in TAMR, for the purpose of selecting the most suitable area.

Central-East Turneffe Area for Restoration		
Metric	Pros	Cons
Practicality	Proximity to Conservation Outpost, Within a marine protected area	Windward exposure
Abundance/Richness	Moderate abundance, High richness	-
Key Taxa	PAST, AGAR, ORBI present in all sites, All key taxa appear at least once	PPOR, ACRO, CNAT, DLAB, PSEU absent in some sites
Bleaching Presence	Low-Moderate	Temporal variation in surveys may have affected bleaching prevalence
SCTLD Presence	Low	-
Disease Presence	Very Low	-

Table 6. Summary of species characteristics for recommended species for restoration at TAMR

Recommend Species	Species Traits	Historical Presence	Current Presence	Reproductive Mode
<i>Orbicella spp.</i>	Reef Framework Building (generalist life history, moderate vulnerability to SCTLD, massive structure)	Yes	Present across the atoll	Recruits not observed
<i>Agaricia spp.</i>	Reef Framework Building (weedy life history, low vulnerability to SCTLD, foliose-encrusting structure)	Yes	Present across the atoll	Recruits observed in good numbers
<i>Acropora spp.</i>	Reef Framework Building Competitive life history, undocumented vulnerability to SCTLD, branching structure)	Yes	Absent from most of the atoll, except two localities in the central-east	Recruits not observed

Acknowledgements

We extend our sincere gratitude to all who contributed to the successful completion of this coral assessment. We especially recognize the field data collectors - Anthony Lizama and Elias Alamina (UB-ERI), Wilbert Castillo and Jeissen Mattu (Independent), and Daniel McLaughlin, Fara Maza, and Kevin Novelo (TASA) - for their commitment and professionalism during the assessment. Special thanks to the captains - Berris Torres, Everal McCulloch, Carlitos Ramos, Jairo Osorio, Kiefer Alvarez - and logistics personnel who facilitated safe and efficient field operations.

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Appendix

Appended Table 1. Comprehensive list of coral species surveyed and trait classifications.

No	Species Code	Species	Coral Traits (Darling, 2012)	SCTLD Susceptibility (Lee Hing, 2024; Papke, 2024)	Coral Shape (Alvarez-Filip, 2011)
1	AAGA	<i>Agaricia agaricites</i>	Weedy	Low	Platy-Folaceous-Encrusting
2	ACER	<i>Acropora cervicornis</i>	Competitive	NA	Branching-Ramose-Phaceloid
3	AFRA	<i>Agaricia fragilis</i>	Weedy	Low	Platy-Folaceous-Encrusting
4	AHUM	<i>Agaricia humilis</i>	Weedy	Low	Massive-Nodular
5	ALAM	<i>Agaricia lamarcki</i>	Weedy	Low	Platy-Folaceous-Encrusting
6	ATEN	<i>Agaricia tenuifolia</i>	Weedy	Low	Platy-Folaceous-Encrusting
7	CNAT	<i>Colpophyllia natans</i>	Stress-tolerant	High	Massive-Nodular
8	DCYL	<i>Dendrogyra cylindrus</i>	Competitive	High	Massive-Nodular
9	DLAB	<i>Diploria labyrinthiformis</i>	Stress-tolerant	High	Massive-Nodular
10	DSTO	<i>Dichocoenia stokesii</i>	Stress-tolerant	High	Massive-Nodular
11	EFAS	<i>Eusmilia fastigiata</i>	Stress-tolerant	High	Branching-Ramose-Phaceloid
12	FFRA	<i>Favia fragum</i>	Stress-tolerant	Low	Massive-Nodular
13	HCUC	<i>Helioseris cucullata</i>	Weedy	Low	Platy-Folaceous-Encrusting
14	IRIG	<i>Isophyllia rigida</i>	Weedy	Low	Massive-Nodular
15	MALC	<i>Millepora alcicornis</i>	Weedy	NA	Branching-Ramose-Phaceloid
16	MALI	<i>Mycetophyllia aliciae</i>	Weedy	Low	Platy-Folaceous-Encrusting
17	MARE	<i>Manicina areolata</i>	Weedy	Low	Massive-Nodular
18	MAUR	<i>Madracis auretenra</i>	Weedy	Low	Branching-Ramose-Phaceloid
19	MCAV	<i>Montastraea cavernosa</i>	Stress-tolerant	Moderate	Massive-Nodular
20	MCOM	<i>Millepora complanata</i>	Weedy	NA	Platy-Folaceous-Encrusting
21	MDEC	<i>Madracis decactis</i>	Weedy	Low	Massive-Nodular
22	MJAC	<i>Meandrina jacksoni</i>	Weedy	High	Massive-Nodular
23	MLAM	<i>Mycetophyllia lamarckiana</i>	Weedy	Low	Platy-Folaceous-Encrusting
24	MMEA	<i>Meandrina meandrites</i>	Stress-tolerant	High	Massive-Nodular

25	MYCE	<i>Mycetophyllia</i>	Weedy	Low	Platy-Folaceous-Encrusting
26	OANN	<i>Orbicella annularis</i>	Generalist	Moderate	Massive-Nodular
27	OFAV	<i>Orbicella faveolata</i>	Generalist	Moderate	Massive-Nodular
28	OFRA	<i>Orbicella franksi</i>	Generalist	Moderate	Massive-Nodular
29	PAST	<i>Porites astreoides</i>	Weedy	Low	Massive-Nodular
30	PCLI	<i>Pseudodiploria clivosa</i>	Stress-tolerant	High	Massive-Nodular
31	PDIG	<i>Digitate Porites</i>	Weedy	Low	Branching-Ramose-Phaceloid
32	PDIV	<i>Porites divaricata</i>	Weedy	Low	Branching-Ramose-Phaceloid
33	PFUR	<i>Porites furcata</i>	Weedy	Low	Branching-Ramose-Phaceloid
34	PPOR	<i>Porites porites</i>	Weedy	Low	Branching-Ramose-Phaceloid
35	PSTR	<i>Pseudodiploria strigosa</i>	Stress-tolerant	High	Massive-Nodular
36	SBOU	<i>Solenastrea bournoni</i>	Stress-tolerant	Moderate	Massive-Nodular
37	SCUB	<i>Scolymia cubensis</i>	Stress-tolerant	Low	Massive-Nodular
38	SINT	<i>Stephanocoenia intersepta</i>	Stress-tolerant	Moderate	Massive-Nodular
39	SRAD	<i>Siderastrea radians</i>	Weedy	Moderate	Massive-Nodular
40	SSID	<i>Siderastrea siderea</i>	Stress-tolerant	Moderate	Massive-Nodular
